

Massive Intestinal Prolapse Through the Vagina (Enterocoele)

Case Report

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Abstract

We present the case of an 83-year old female patient with a 3-day history of an obvious vaginal bulge. The patient's medical history was important only for psychotic disorder and uterine prolapse, which the patient habitually reduced with her hands. Physical examination revealed prolapse of the small intestine (measuring 1 m in length) through vagina without peritoneal coverage. During surgery, a breach was recognized in the peritoneum as well as a defect in the right lateral vaginal wall, through which both cecum and small intestine prolapsed. Having determined small intestinal viability intraoperatively, the enterocele was reduced and the peritoneal breach was closed with a continuous running suture and a mesh. The vaginal defect was corrected by sutures and the repair was augmented by mesh. Finally, a pessary was placed inside the patient's vagina. The postoperative course was uneventful and the patient was discharged six days later.

Keywords

Enterocoele, Intestinal prolapse, Vagina

Introduction

Pelvic organ prolapse is the abnormal descent or herniation of the pelvic organs from their normal attachment sites or their normal position in the pelvis. Pelvic structures that may be involved include uterus (uterine prolapse), vaginal apex (apical vaginal prolapse), anterior vagina (cystocele), posterior vagina (rectocele) and small intestine (enterocoele) [1].

Pelvic floor defects may be created as a result of childbirth and are caused by the stretching and tearing of the endopelvic fascia, the levator muscles and perineal body. Pregnancy itself, without vaginal birth, has also been cited as a risk factor. Other medical conditions that may result in prolapse are

those associated with increases in intra-abdominal pressure (eg, obesity, chronic pulmonary disease, smoking, constipation). Certain rare abnormalities in connective tissue (collagen), such as Marfan disease, have also been linked to genitourinary prolapse [2].

Symptomatic pelvic organ prolapse can be treated conservatively or surgically. Pelvic surgical procedures may be vaginal, abdominal, laparoscopic, or a combination of these [1].

Case presentation

We present the case of an 83-year old, mentally impaired, female patient with a 3-day history of an obvious vaginal bulge. The patient's medical history was important only for uterine prolapse, diagnosed 5 years earlier, which the patient habitually reduced with her hands. Furthermore, she was treated with amp Risperidone 50mg and Olanzapine 20mg for her psychotic disorder, which accounted for the delay in the diagnosis of the problem. Physical examination revealed prolapse of the small intestine (measuring 1 m in length), macroscopically ischaemic, through the vagina, without peritoneal coverage (Fig.1). Significant laboratory analyses included a haematocrit of 38, 3%, a CRP value of 8,81mg/dl and a white blood cell (WBC) count of $25,3 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$. Gynaecological manoeuvres were impossible due to small bowel evisceration. The patient was taken to the operating room by a surgical team consisting of both a gynaecologist and general surgeon. With the patient lying in a lithotomy position and under general anesthesia, a lower midline laparotomy was performed by the surgeon. After examination of the abdomen, a breach was identified in the peritoneum as well as a defect in the right lateral vaginal wall, through which both cecum and small intestine prolapsed. Due to narrowness of the breach, reduction of the intestines was impossible without the risk of damaging them. The breach was surgically widened and reduction of the ischemic intestines and cecum was undertaken (Fig. 2). After intraoperative determination of small intestinal viability, it was decided that the pelvis (genitalia, ligaments) should not be

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simultaneously subjected to further intervention due to prolonged exteriorization of the intestine. The peritoneal breach was closed with a continuous running suture using delayed absorbable sutures and a mesh. The vaginal defect (Fig. 3) was corrected by sutures and the repair was augmented by mesh. Finally, a pessary was placed inside the patient's vagina. The postoperative course was uneventful and the patient was discharged six days later. During the 1-month follow-up period, the patient remained asymptomatic.

Fig. 1 Intestinal prolapse through vagina without peritoneal coverage

Fig. 2 Reduction of small intestine and cecum into the peritoneal cavity

Fig. 3 Breach in the right lateral vaginal wall

Discussion

Pelvic organ prolapse is the abnormal descent or herniation of the pelvic organs from their normal attachment sites or their normal position in the pelvis. Vaginal vault prolapse may be found in a patient with a previous hysterectomy. An enterocele is a true herniation of the peritoneum and small bowel through the upper posterior portion of the vagina [3]. Pelvic organs are mainly supported by the levator muscles of perineum. The cardinal-uterosacral ligament complex keeps pelvic organs in an anatomic position, where they can be supported by muscle activity. Loss of these normal supportive mechanisms leads to pelvic organ prolapse [1].

As concerns enterocele, the definition is somewhat more difficult. Previous texts have defined enterocele as any intraperitoneal contents (bowel or mesentery) palpable within the cul-de-sac, as evaluated during an examination in the erect position. A more anatomic definition was proposed by Richardson, who suggested that enterocele occurs when endopelvic fascia does not intervene between the peritoneum and vagina [4].

The underlying mechanism that predisposes a patient to most of these conditions is loss of normal pelvic support via several possible causes. As a rule, the most common etiology stems from trauma from childbirth or hysterectomy. Other possible causes arise from traumatic or surgical injury, heavy physical labor, chronic coughing, congenital defects, postmenopausal tissue atrophy from hormonal changes and prior corrective surgery for prolapse [2].

In a review of the literature in 1996, Virtanen et al. reported a total of 72 cases. In their series, 56% of patients had undergone one or more vaginal operations and 14% of eviscerations occurred after abdominal hysterectomy. Enterocele was the most common risk factor noted in 34% of patients, and straining at stool was an associated factor in 18% of

cases. Since 1996, an additional 14 cases have been reported and 12 of these have occurred after pelvic surgery, including abdominal hysterectomy, vaginal hysterectomy, radical hysterectomy, laparoscopic hysterectomy and colpocleisis [5-13].

In our case, the exteriorized vaginal bulge constituted a complicated enterocele, as the intestines were not covered by peritoneum. It is likely that the breach of peritoneum continuity had been caused by the patient herself, while trying to reduce the enterocele with her hands. There is no mention of a similar case in the bibliography.

Asymptomatic pelvic organ prolapse needs no treatment. Non-surgical (conservative) management of pelvic organ prolapse is recommended by both the Agency for Health Care Policy and Research and the ACOG Committee on Practice Bulletins and should be attempted before surgery is contemplated (pelvic muscle exercises, vaginal support devices-pessaries, topical estradiol cream or systemic estrogen therapy) [14].

Surgery to repair enterocele and apical prolapse should address the underlying defect-specific pathophysiology of the patient's condition and should restore normal anatomy. This includes addressing all 3 levels of vaginal support [15], with restoration of the normal vaginal axis and the integrity of the endopelvic fascia in all of its compartments. Pelvic surgical procedures can be vaginal, abdominal, laparoscopic, or a combination of these. Surgical techniques can be reconstructive, with the aim of restoring anatomy and maintaining the potential for coitus, or include destructive procedures that eliminate prolapse at the expense of potential coital function [16].

Furthermore, treatment and prevention of enterocele requires proper orientation of the upper vagina in a near-horizontal plane (in the erect position) and reestablishment of endopelvic fascial integrity. Culdoplasty is performed in order to close the posterior cul-de-sac and further direct the vaginal apex toward the hollow of the sacrum. The most commonly performed culdoplasties include the McCall, Moschowitz, and Halban methods. Culdoplasty does not, however, address the underlying endopelvic fascial defects at the vaginal apex. Consequently, re-establishing continuity of the endopelvic fascia at the apex is achieved by re-approximating the pubocervical fascia with the rectovaginal fascia at the most proximal end [17].

In our patient, prolonged evisceration of the intestines could not permit further intervention in the pelvis at the same time. In order to prevent recurrent enterocele, vaginal repair was augmented by

mesh and the patient was offered a vaginal support device (VSD, pessary). According to several authors, mesh augmentation decreases the expected incidence of severe recurrent vaginal prolapse. As a result, vaginal surgery using mesh and a VSD is an effective procedure for pelvic organ prolapse [18-21].

According to the literature, even in this setting, uterine suspension could have proved beneficial. Many methods of uterine suspension have been reported, including sacrospinous ligament suspension, abdominal sacral colpopexy and uterosacral ligament suspension.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Μαζική Πρόπτωση Ελίκων Εντέρου διά του Κόλπου (Εντεροκήλη)

Ενδιαφέρουσα Περίπτωση

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Περίληψη

Παρουσιάζουμε την περίπτωση ασθενούς 83 ετών η οποία προσήλθε αιτώμενη εμφανή προπίπτουσα μάζα από τον κόλπο της, από τριημέρου. Το ατομικό αναμνηστικό της ασθενούς ήταν αξιοσημείωτο μόνο ως προς μία ψυχωσική διαταραχή και την πρόπτωση μήτρας, την οποία η ασθενής συνήθιζε να ανατάσσει με τα χέρια της. Η φυσική εξέταση απεκάλυψε πρόπτωση ελίκων λεπτού εντέρου, μήκους ενός μέτρου, διαμέσου του κόλπου χωρίς επικάλυψη από περιτόναιο. Διεγχειρητικά αναγνωρίστηκε χάσμα στο περιτόναιο καθώς και έλλειμμα στο δεξιό πλάγιο τοίχωμα του κόλπου, μέσα από το οποίο προέπιπταν τόσο το λεπτό έντερο όσο και τμήμα του τυφλού. Μετά από χειρουργική διεύρυνση του χάσματος στο περιτόναιο, προκειμένου να αναταχθεί με ασφάλεια το έντερο, καθώς και έλεγχο της βιωσιμότητάς του, πραγματοποιήθηκε ανάταξη των σπλάχνων εντός της κοιλίας. Το περιτοναϊκό χάσμα συγκλείστηκε με συνεχή ραφή και πλέγμα, ενώ και η συρραφή του κόλπου ενίσχυθηκε με πλέγμα. Η μετεγχειρητική πορεία ήταν ανεπίπλεκτη και η ασθενής έλαβε εξιτήριο έξι μέρες αργότερα. Ένα μήνα μετά η ασθενής παρέμενε ασυμπτωματική.

Λεξεις Κλειδιά

Εντεροκήλη, Πρόπτωση εντέρου, Κόλπος